

Some Mixed Tertiary Butoxysilanes

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The syntheses of tetratertiarybutoxy and some mixed tertiarybutoxysilanes have been described.

In recent years considerable interest has been aroused in the synthesis of alkoxy and mixed alkoxysilanes. The general method employed has been to allow the tetrachloride to react directly with the alcohol. However, the nature of the alcohol greatly affects the reaction. While reactions of the lower alcohols like methanol and ethanol with the tetrachloride appear to be quite straightforward and facile, the same does not hold good for alcohols with ramified alkyl groups, e.g., the alcohols having tertiary alkyl groups. There is always the possibility of some side reaction taking place when tertiary alcohols are allowed to combine directly with the tetrachloride and this generally leads to the formation of hydrolysed products¹.

Ridge and Todd² appear to have first attempted the reaction between tetrachlorosilane and tertiary butanol and reported their failure to prepare tetratertiarybutoxysilane. Instead, tertiary butyl chloride and silica were obtained as the products of the reaction.

Miner and coworkers³ carried out the reaction between tetrachlorosilane and tertiary butanol in pyridine medium. Although they could not prepare tetratertiarybutoxysilane, they succeeded in preparing compounds of the type, $\text{SiCl}_3(\text{OR})$, $\text{SiCl}_2(\text{OR})_2$, and $\text{SiCl}(\text{OR})_3$, where $\text{R}=\text{Bu}^t$ or OMe_2Et . Thus they were unable to cause the replacement of the last chlorine atom of tetrachlorosilane by tertiary alkoxy group. The non-replacement of the last chlorine atom in tritertiarybutoxychlorosilane by the fourth tertiary alkoxy group is obviously due to steric factors, which can be understood on the basis of small ionic radius of silicon.

Since the sodium alkoxide in alcohol is a much more active reagent than the alcohol itself, Breederveld *et al.*⁴ prepared tetratertiarybutoxysilane by causing the tetrabromosilane to react with sodium tertiary butoxide in petroleum ether medium and obtained the compound in about 37% yield.

Hyde and Curry⁵ have obtained good yields of tetratertiarybutoxysilane by causing the tetrafluorosilane to react with sodium tertiary butoxide. After refluxing a

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1. Bradley, D. C., Wardlaw, W. and Whitley, A., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 726.

2. Ridge, D. and Todd, (Miss) M., *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2637.

3. Miner, C. S., Bryan, L. A., Holyas, R. P. and Pedlow, G. W., *Ind. Eng. Chem., Ind. Ed.*, 1947, 39, 1868; *Chem. Abs.*, 1948, 42, 517.

4. Breederveld, H. and Waterman, H. I., *Rec. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas*, 1934, 73, 871.

5. Hyde, J. F. and Curry, J. W., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 3140.

mixture of the two, sodium fluoride was removed by filtration and the solution was fractionally distilled under reduced pressure. Tetratertiarybutoxysilane was obtained at 105-105.5°/15 mm.

During the present investigations, tetratertiarybutoxysilane has been synthesised by the disproportionation of mixed tertiarybutoxy-n-octyloxysilane obtained by the reaction of ditertiarybutoxydichlorosilane with n-octanol. By this method not only tetratertiarybutoxysilane was obtained as the product of disproportionation, but several mixed silico orthoesters were also obtained.

Tetrachlorosilane (1 mole) was introduced into a solution of tertiary butanol (2 moles) dissolved in pyridine, keeping the reaction mixture at as low a temperature as possible. When n-octanol (2 moles) was added, a highly exothermic reaction took place. After filtering the precipitated pyridinium hydrochloride, the filtrate was first refluxed and then fractionated under reduced pressure. Many mixed orthoesters were obtained.

In the following table are given the compounds prepared during the course of these investigations;

S. No.	Compound	b.p./mm
1.	$\text{Si}(\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9^t)_4$	72-73°/2
2.	$(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{O}^t)_3\text{Si}(\text{OC}_8\text{H}_{17}^n)$	102-4°/0.7
3.	$(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{O}^t)_2\text{Si}(\text{OC}_8\text{H}_{17}^n)_2$	144°/0.4
4.	$(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{O}^t)\text{Si}(\text{OC}_8\text{H}_{17}^n)_3$	190-5°/0.3

EXPERIMENTAL

All-glass apparatus with interchangeable joints was used throughout. Special precautions were taken to exclude moisture.

Materials: Tetrachlorosilane was a commercial product of the laboratory reagent grade and was distilled before use; b.p. 59.6°.

Pyridine (B.D.H., A.R.) was first refluxed over potassium hydroxide pellets and was finally fractionated over aluminium isopropoxide; b.p. 115.3°.

Normal octanol was freshly distilled before use; b.p. 194.5°.

Analytical Method; Silicon was estimated by digestion of the compound with a small amount of H_2SO_4 (conc.) followed by the addition of a few drops of HNO_3 (conc.) and slowly ignited to dioxide.

After adding tetrachlorosilane (55.0 g) into a well cooled solution of tertiary butanol (47.5 g) taken in pyridine (121.3 g), the mixture was allowed to stand for about 2 hours. On adding n-octanol (85.6 g), a large amount of heat was liberated. The contents were shaken, allowed to stand, filtered and washed with benzene ($\approx$ 100 ml). The filtrate ($\approx$ 200 ml) with a little cloudiness (probably due to slowly forming pyridinium hydrochloride) at the bottom was refluxed for about 6 hours (bath temperature 140°) and again filtered.

This filtrate was then distilled under reduced pressure (bath temperature 150-170°), when some stuff distilled over at 70°/1-2 mm. The remaining liquid was then kept in the

refluxing state for about 8 hours at 200-220°/10-12 mm. After the pressure was reduced to 1-2 mm, two fractions were collected.

- (i) A fraction* (21g) upto 140°/1-mm which had some turbidity and which on subsequent filtration gave a colourless liquid (20.4 g.)
 (ii) Another colourless fraction† (35.0 g) at 180-210°/1.6 mm.

** Refractionation of the first fraction*

The filtrate of the first fraction was subjected to careful refractionation in a semi-micro distillation assembly. About half a gram of the distillate collected upto 70°/2 mm was obtained, when the temperature of the distillate appeared to become steady at about 72-3°/2 mm. This fraction was, therefore, separately collected as (a).

The temperature of the distilling liquid then again rose slowly and appeared to be steady at 100°/0.8 mm. The receiver was, therefore, again changed at this stage and another fraction (b) was collected between 100-5°/0.8 mm.

After the distillate (≈ 7 g) had been collected, the rate of collection of the distilling liquid showed a decrement and therefore, the bath temperature was raised when distillation started slowly. This middle fraction was again collected in a separate flask and the receiver was changed when the temperature of distillation became steady at about 143-4°/0.4 mm, when fraction (c) was collected.

The amounts and analyses of the three separate fractions are given below:

- (a) 4.0 g, b. p. 72-3°/2 mm. Found: Si, 8.70. $(C_4H_9O^t)_4$ Si requires Si, 8.76%.

This clear distillate was further redistilled, when again a colourless liquid was obtained at 46°/0.4 mm or 72°/2 mm. Found: Si, 8.85%.

- (b) 7.0 g, b. p. 100-5°/0.8 mm. Found: Si, 8.06. $(C_4H_9O^t)_3$ Si $(OC_8H_{17}^n)$ requires Si, 7.45%.

This fraction was redistilled and the fraction passing over 102-4°/0.7 mm was collected separately and reanalysed. Found: Si, 7.51%.

- (c) 4.0 g, b. p. 144°/0.4 mm. Found: Si, 6.63. $(C_4H_9O^t)_2$ Si $(OC_8H_{17}^n)_2$ requires Si, 6.48%.

† Refractionation of the second fraction

The second fraction was also subjected to refractionation and the liquid distilling upto about 150°/0.3 mm was rapidly collected in a separate flask. The bath temperature was then raised when distillation started slowly and the temperature of the distilling liquid rose gradually upto about 195°/0.3 mm, after which it became somewhat steady. The receiver was again changed and the fraction (8.0 g) distilling at 190-5°/0.3 mm was collected separately. Found: Si, 5.68%

$(C_4H_9O^t)$ Si $(OC_8H_{17}^n)_2$ requires Si, 5.74%.